

TEACHER'S CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN THE NEW NORMAL: INPUT FOR DEVELOPING THE PUPILS' 21ST- CENTURY SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study dealt with the “teacher’s classroom management practices to the developing the pupils’ 21st century skills in the new normal in the Division of Batangas. The descriptive method of research was utilized to assess the “teacher’s classroom management practices to the development of 4c’s (critical thinking, creativity and innovation .collaboration, communication) as the pupils’ 21st century skills. The 1005 respondents of the study were composed teachers from Area III with the total number of eleven (11) districts from Public Elementary Schools in the Division of Batangas.during the Academic Year 2020-2021.The salient findings of the study were as follows; teachers age 42-46 years old and above (39.70%) ; female (92.03%); had 21-25 years in service (49.25%), with a Master’s Degree and EdD/PhD units (44.9%) ; holding Teacher III position (39.40%) ; and have General Education specialization (38.80%).The teacher perceived there level of classroom management practices on the five domains; a. maximize structure and predictability; b. post, teach, review, monitor and reinforce expectations; c. engage students in observable ways; d. continuum of strategies to acknowledge appropriate behavior, and e.continuum of strategies to respond to inappropriate behavior were “observed”. However the level of the development of pupils’ 21st-century skills in critical thinking, creativity and innovation, collaboration, communication, majority of the teachers’ responses was “to a great extent”. The study displayed that the ages, gender, length in service, and educational attainment were significantly related to the classroom management practices of the teachers in the new normal for the development of pupils' 21st-century skills. It demonstrates the older the teacher become the more mature in handling their classroom management practices in the field, the longer they stayed in the service ; the higher educational attainment they earn in their field greatly affects the development of the students 21st-century skills. All classroom management practices revealed significant with the development of pupils’ critical thinking, creativity and innovation, and communication, collaboration 21st-century skills. Three domains of classroom management practices post, teach, review, monitor, and reinforce expectations; engage students in observable ways, and continuum of strategies to respond to inappropriate behavior were significant variables of pupil’s 21st -century skills .

Keywords: new normal, classroom practices, 21st-century skills, teachers, pupils, Philippines